

Regularity and Paracompactness in Fuzzy Topological Spaces

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ABSTRACT. In this paper we obtain two characterizations of regular fuzzy topological spaces using Luo's and Abd El-Monsef and others' paracompact fuzzy topological spaces.

1. Introduction

In this paper we obtain two characterizations of fuzzy regularity as a fuzzy covering property. Indeed, we show that one can characterize fuzzy regularity as a paracompact-type fuzzy property in Luo's and Abd El-Monsef and others' both senses.

2. Definitions and Main Results

Definition 1 [1] Let μ be a set in a fts (X, τ) and let $r \in (0, 1]$, $s \in [0, 1)$; we define

$$\mu_{[r]} = \chi_{\{x \in X; \mu(x) \geq r\}}$$

$$\mu_{(s)} = \chi_{\{x \in X; \mu(x) > s\}}$$

$$\mu_{\langle r \rangle} = r\mu_{[r]}$$

Definition 2 [1] Let $\mathcal{A}$ be a family of sets and μ be a set in a fts (X, τ) . We say that $\mathcal{A}$ is locally finite (resp. *-locally finite) in μ for each point e in μ , there exists $v \in Q(e)$ such that v

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is quasi-coincident (resp. intersects) with at most a finite number of sets of $\mathcal{A}$; we often omit the word "in μ " when $\mu = X$.

Definition 3 [1] A family of sets $\mathcal{A}$ is called a Q -cover of a set μ if for each $x \in \text{supp}(\mu)$, there exist a $\nu \in \mathcal{A}$ such that ν and μ are quasi-coincident at x . Let $r \in (0,1]$. $\mathcal{A}$ is called a $r-Q$ cover of μ if $\mathcal{A}$ is a Q -cover of $\mu_{(r)}$.

Definition 4 [1] Let $r \in (0,1]$, μ be a set in a fts (X, τ) . We say that μ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) if for each r -open Q -cover of μ there exists an open refinement of it which is both locally finite (resp. $*$ -locally finite) in μ and a $r-Q$ -cover of μ . The fuzzy set μ is called S -paracompact (resp. S^* -paracompact) if for every $r \in (0,1]$, μ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact).

Definition 5 [2] A family of fuzzy sets $\mathcal{U}$ is called an L -cover of a fuzzy set μ if $\bigvee_{\nu \in \mathcal{U}} \nu \geq \mu$.

Definition 6 [2] Let μ be a fuzzy set in a fts (X, τ) . We say that μ is fuzzy paracompact (resp. $*$ -fuzzy paracompact) if for each open L -cover $\mathcal{B}$ of μ and for each $\xi \in (0,1]$, there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{B}^*$ of $\mathcal{B}$ which is both locally finite (resp. $*$ -locally finite) in μ and L -cover of $\mu - \xi$. We say that a fts (X, τ) is fuzzy paracompact (resp. $*$ -fuzzy paracompact) if each constant set in X is fuzzy paracompact (resp. $*$ -fuzzy paracompact).

Theorem 1 Let (X, τ) a fuzzy Hausdorff fts (in any of Wuyts and Lowen's definitions that are good extensions of Hausdorffness). Then (X, τ) is fuzzy regular if and only if for each $r \in (0,1]$, for each r -open Q -cover of (X, τ) and for each fuzzy point x_λ of X there exists an open refinement of it which is both $*$ -locally finite in x_λ and a $r-Q$ -cover of (X, τ) .

Proof ($\Rightarrow$) For each $r \in (0,1]$, let $\mathcal{U}$ be a r -open Q -cover of (X, τ) , and x_λ be a fuzzy point of X . Then, we have that the family of crisp sets $\{U_{(1-r)} \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\}$, is an open cover of $(X, [\tau])$, which is Hausdorff and regular ([3], [4]). Then ([5], [6], [7]), it has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}_x \subset [\tau]$

which is a cover of X , and is locally finite in x . For each $V \in \mathcal{V}_x$ we have an $U_V \in \mathcal{U}$ with $V \subset (U_V)_{(1-r)}$.

Let $\mathcal{W}_x = \{\chi_V \wedge U_V \mid V \in \mathcal{V}_x\}$. Then, $\mathcal{W}_x \subset \tau$, is both an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ and a $r-Q$ -cover of (X, τ) , and also is $*$ -locally finite in x_λ , indeed, because $\mathcal{V}_x$ is locally finite in x , we have an open neighborhood G of x that G intersects with only finite number of members of $\mathcal{V}_x$. Then $\chi_G \in Q(x_\lambda)$ intersects with only a finite number of members of $\mathcal{W}_x$.

($\Leftarrow$) Let $\mathcal{U} \subset [\tau]$ be an open cover of $(X, [\tau])$; then $\{\chi_U \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\}$ is an open Q -cover of 1_X , and, for each $x \in X$, it has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}_{x_r}$ which is a Q -cover of 1_X and also locally finite in x_{1-r} . Let $\mathcal{W} = \{V_{(1-r)} \mid V \in \mathcal{V}_{x_r}\}$; then $\mathcal{W} \subset [\tau]$ is both a refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ and a cover of $(X, [\tau])$. Also, $\mathcal{W}$ is locally finite in x . Indeed: we take $O_1 \in Q(x_{1-r})$ such that O_1 is quasi-coincident with only a finite number of members $V_1, \dots, V_n$, of $\mathcal{V}_{x_r}$. Let $O = (O_1)_{(r)}$, then $x \in O \in [\tau]$. For each $V \in \mathcal{V}_{x_r}$, if $O \wedge V_{(1-r)} \neq \emptyset$, we have a crisp point $y \in X$, such that $O_1(y) > r$, $V(y) > 1-r$, $O_1(y) + V(y) > 1$, then $O_1 q V$ and $V \in \{V_1, \dots, V_n\}$. Hence the neighborhood O of x intersects with only a finite number of members $(V_1)_{(1-r)}, \dots, (V_n)_{(1-r)} \in \mathcal{W}$.

Theorem 2. Let (X, τ) be a fuzzy Hausdorff fts (in any of Wuyts and Lowen's definitions that are good extensions of Hausdorffness [3]). Then (X, τ) is fuzzy regular if and only if for each $r \in I$, and for each open L -cover $\mathcal{B}$ of r , for each $\xi \in (0, 1]$, and for each fuzzy point x_λ of X , there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{B}^*$ of it which is both $*$ -locally finite in x_λ and L -cover of $r - \xi$.

Proof ($\Rightarrow$) For each $r \in I$, and for each open L -cover $\mathcal{B}$ of r , for each $\xi \in (0, 1]$, and for each fuzzy point x_λ of X , we have that the family of crisp sets $\mathcal{U} = \{G^{-1}((r - \xi, 1]) \mid G \in \mathcal{B}\} \subset [\tau]$ is an open cover of $(X, [\tau])$ which is Hausdorff and regular ([3, 4]). Then ([5],[6],[7]), it has an open refinement $\mathcal{U}_x^* \subset [\tau]$ which is a cover of X and is locally finite in x . For each $V \in \mathcal{U}_x^*$, there

exists $G_V^{-1}((r-\xi, 1]) \in \mathcal{U}$, such that $V \subset G_V^{-1}((r-\xi, 1])$. So $\mathcal{B}^* = \{\chi_V \wedge G_V | V \in \mathcal{U}_x^*\} \subset \tau$ is refinement of $\mathcal{B}$. Then, there exists $V \in \mathcal{U}_x^*$ such that $x \in V$ and $G_V(x) > r - \xi$. So, $(\chi_V \wedge G_V)(x) \geq r - \xi$, and $\bigvee \{\chi_V \wedge G_V | V \in \mathcal{U}_x^*\} \geq r - \xi$. Since $\mathcal{U}_x^*$ is locally finite in x , there exists $A \in [\tau]$ with $x \in A$, such that intersects with at most a finite number of members of $\mathcal{U}_x^*$. Then, there exists $\chi_A \in \tau$ such that $x_\lambda \in \chi_A$ and χ_A intersects with a finite number of fuzzy sets of $\mathcal{B}^*$.

($\Leftarrow$) Let $\mathcal{U} \subset [\tau]$ be an open cover of X and $x \in X$, then $\mathcal{B} = \{\chi_U | U \in \mathcal{U}\}$ is an open L -cover of (X, τ) and for each, $r \in I$ is $\bigvee \{\chi_U | U \in \mathcal{U}\} \geq r$. For each $\xi \in (0, 1]$, there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{B}^*$ of $\mathcal{B}$ which is both locally finite in x_λ and L -cover of $r - \xi$. This implies that $\bigvee \{G | G \in \mathcal{B}^*\} \geq r - \xi_1$ for all $\xi_1 > \xi$. Let $\mathcal{U}^* = \{G^{-1}((r-\xi, 1]) | G \in \mathcal{B}^*\}$, then $\mathcal{U}^* \subset [\tau]$ is an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ (indeed, for each $G^{-1}((r-\xi, 1]) \in \mathcal{U}^*$ there exists $V_G \in \mathcal{U}$ such that $G^{-1}((r-\xi, 1]) \subset V_G$). Since $\bigvee \{G | G \in \mathcal{B}^*\} \geq r - \xi_1$, then $\mathcal{U}^*$ is an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}$. And, since $x \in X$ there exists $A \in \mathcal{Q}(x_\lambda)$ which intersects with only $G_1, \dots, G_n \in \mathcal{B}^*$. Since $A(x) + \lambda > 1$, we have $A(x) > 1 - \lambda$, then $x \in A^{-1}((1 - \lambda, 1]) \in [\tau]$.

If $A^{-1}((1 - \lambda, 1]) \cap G^{-1}((r - \xi, 1]) \neq \emptyset$, there exists some point z , such that $A(z) > 1 - \lambda$ and $G(z) > r - \xi$, so $A \wedge G \neq \emptyset$. Then, if the neighborhood $A^{-1}((1 - \lambda, 1])$ of x intersects with infinite members of $\mathcal{U}^*$, A intersects with infinite members of $\mathcal{B}^*$. Thus $\mathcal{U}^*$ is locally finite in x .

This yields that the Hausdorff topological space $(X, [\tau])$ is regular ([5], [6], [7]) and (X, τ) is fuzzy regular ([4]).

3. Discussion

In this paper, fuzzy regularity is characterized as a fuzzy covering property. Future research could obtain characterization of other fuzzy separation properties as fuzzy covering properties.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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